

A STUDY TO ASSESS MENOPAUSAL SYMPTOMS AND QUALITY OF LIFE OF POST-MENOPAUSAL WOMEN RESIDING AT TRIBAL AREA OF BHANDARDARA

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Abstract :

Background : Average age of menopause for Indian women is 48 years to 55 years. In some women, early menopause occurs during the age of 45 to 50 years and in some other women, 'premature menopause' is observed which occurs naturally before 40 years of age. Studies reveal that postmenopausal women are at a high risk of several health issues which include osteoporosis, cardiovascular ailments, obesity etc. There are some studies on the postmenopausal health status of women from different parts of the world but there is not much report from South East Asian countries. Due to increasing population in India, the number of postmenopausal women is also rising in India. Thus, post-menopausal women health issues seek major attention in India.

Methods : The research methodology is a scientific and systematic way of finding a solution to a problem. The methodology of the study includes the description of research design and research approach, setting of the study, sample, sampling technique, developing and testing of tool, method of data collection and plan of data analysis based on the study objectives and hypothesis.

Result : The present study assesses the post-menopausal QOL of the study participants, it reveals that, majority 43% of the participants had good quality of life, followed by 41% of the participants had average quality of life, and 16% of the participants had poor quality of life.

A similar study was conducted to assess the effects of menopausal symptoms on the QOL using Menopause-Specific QOL Questionnaire (MENQOL) among women in India. The study findings reveal that, the prevalence of symptoms in physical, vasomotor, psychological, and sexual domains was 74.56%, 60.7%, 44.68%, and 26.4%, respectively. An overall mean MENQOL score of physical (27.1 + 0.72), psychological (2.01 + 0.27), vasomotor (4.08 + 0.79), and sexual (3.89 + 0.59) health-related QOL among menopausal women showed poor QOL. Statistically significant differences were observed between the sociodemographic variables and the health-related QOL scores in all domains at $P < 0.05$. The study concludes that menopausal women-centred integrated model of care would empower women to lead improved health-related QOL in the next one-third of postmenopausal life span development.

Conclusions : The study was performed to assess menopausal symptoms and post-menopausal quality of life of the women residing in tribal area. Majority of the participants found to be experiencing mild to moderate menopausal symptoms and good quality of life. The correlation between menopausal symptoms and post-menopausal quality of life shown strongly negative correlation.

Introduction

Menopause, defined as the end of menstruation due to the loss of ovarian follicular activity, which is known to decrease in the late 30's with complete loss in most women in the early 50's is a phenomenon of increasing concern due to an increase in life expectancy. The number of postmenopausal women worldwide is expected to reach 1.2 billion by 2030. The term 'menopausal transition' can be used synonymously with the term 'peri-menopause'. The period of change in ovarian function from being fertile to becoming infertile, called menopausal transition, is a natural and inevitable change that affects all women. Although, menopause is considered to be a universal phenomenon it is affected by socio-cultural norms, and women's experiences of the menopausal transition is consequently handled by women in different ways.

The quality of life for post-menopausal women is a multifaceted construct influenced by various physiological, psychological, and social factors. Post-menopausal women often experience a range of symptoms such as hot flashes, mood swings, sleep disturbances, and genitourinary changes, which can significantly impact their overall well-being and daily functioning. Moreover, the hormonal shifts associated with menopause contribute to an increased risk of chronic health conditions, including cardiovascular diseases, osteoporosis, and cognitive impairments, further influencing the quality of life. Beyond physical health, psychological factors such as body image concerns, self-esteem, and emotional well-being play a pivotal role in shaping post-menopausal women's quality of life. Social support networks, access to healthcare resources, and individual coping strategies also contribute to the overall quality of life during this life transition. Recognizing the multifactorial nature of quality of life in post-menopausal women is essential for healthcare providers to develop comprehensive care strategies that address the unique needs and challenges faced by this population.

BACKGROUND OF STUDY

Average age of menopause for Indian women is 48 years to 55 years. In some women, early menopause occurs during the age of 45 to 50 years and in some other women, 'premature menopause' is observed which occurs naturally before 40 years of age. Studies reveal that postmenopausal women are at a high risk of several health issues which include osteoporosis, cardiovascular ailments, obesity etc. There are some studies on the postmenopausal health status of women from different parts of the world but there is not much report from South East

Asian countries. Due to increasing population in India, the number of postmenopausal women is also rising in India. Thus, post-menopausal women health issues seek major attention in India.

Menopause represents a significant physiological and hormonal shift in women, characterized by the permanent cessation of menstrual periods due to decreased ovarian function and hormonal fluctuations, typically occurring in the late 40s to early 50s. This transitional phase is often accompanied by a myriad of symptoms, including hot flashes, night sweats, mood disturbances, sleep disturbances, and vaginal dryness, which can significantly impact quality of life. Additionally, menopause is associated with an increased risk of various health conditions such as osteoporosis, cardiovascular diseases, and genitourinary complications. Effective management of menopausal symptoms and associated health risks necessitates a holistic approach encompassing hormone replacement therapy, non-hormonal pharmacological interventions, lifestyle modifications, and patient education. By adopting a comprehensive and individualized care strategy, healthcare providers can empower women to navigate the complexities of menopause with confidence, resilience, and improved well-being.

Material and Methods:

The sample for the study was the post-menopausal women residing at tribal area of Bhandardara selected by non-probability purposive sampling technique.

Criteria for selection of sample

Inclusion criteria

The post-menopausal women, who are;

1. of age above 45 years
2. residing at tribal area of Bhandardara
3. willing to participate in the study
4. available during data collection period
5. able understands Marathi, Hindi, and English

Exclusion criteria

The post-menopausal women, who are;

1. undergone hormonal therapy
2. surgical hysterectomy
3. not present at the time of data collection
4. unable to respond to the tool

Operational Definition

Assess :

As per Dictionary- The critical analysis and valuation or judgement of the status or quality of a particular condition, situation, or other subject of appraisal.¹²

In this study- It refers to, assessing the menopausal symptoms and quality of life of post-menopausal womens.

Menopause :

As per Dictionary- The span of time during which the menstrual cycle wanes and gradually stops.¹³

In this study- It refers to, the span of time in the life of tribal women, during which menstrual cycle wanes and stops.

Quality of life :

As per Dictionary- Quality of life (QOL) is defined by the World Health Organization as "an individual's perception of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and concerns".¹⁴

In this study- It refers to, the culture and value systems in which post-menopausal tribal womens live in relation to their goals, expectations, standards, and concerns.

Post-menopausal women

As per Dictionary- A term to describe the time after someone has gone through menopause and has not experienced a period for over a year.¹⁵

In this study- It refers to, the tribal women who has gone through menopause and has not experienced a period for over a year.

Tribal area :

As per Dictionary- Tribal area means areas with a preponderance of tribal population.¹⁶

In this study- It refers to, the areas of Bhandaradara with a preponderance of tribal population.

Sample size and Sampling techniques :

It is a subset of population selected for the particular study and the members of the sample is 100 are the study subject.

The sample for the study was the post-menopausal women residing at tribal area of Bhandardara selected by non-probability purposive sampling technique was used.

Method of data collection

The tool consists of three sections:

Section A: Demographic data of the post-menopausal women

Section A consist of 9 items to collect demographic data of post-menopausal women residing at tribal area of Bhandardara.

Section B: Menopause Rating Scale (MRS) to assess menopausal symptoms among post-menopausal women residing at tribal area of Bhandardara.

Section C: Utian quality of life scale to assess quality of life of post-menopausal women residing at tribal area of Bhandardara.

Results :

Description of the study participant according to their demographic characteristics

This section deals with description of participants according to their demographic characteristics. Frequency and percentage are used to describe the demographic characteristics of study participants.

Table 4.1. Description of study participants according to their demographic characteristics.

n=100

SR.NO.	SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLE		F	%
1	Age	45-50 years	40	40%
		51-55 years	31	31%
		56-60 years	12	13%
		More than 60 years	16	16%
2	Marital Status	Unmarried	0	0%
		Married	91	91%
		Divorced / Widow	9	9%
3	Education	Illiterate	41	41%
		Primary	33	33%
		Secondary/ Higher secondary	24	24%
		Graduation/ Post graduate	2	2%

4	Whether working?	Yes	54	54%
		No	46	46%
5	Occupation	Housewife	44	44%
		Daily wages	20	20%
		Agriculture	13	13%
		Private employee	17	17%
		Government Employee	2	2%
		Self-owned business	4	4%
6	Type of family	Nuclear	51	51%
		Joint	46	46%
		Extended	3	3%
7	Monthly income	<5000	13	13%
		5001-10000	49	49%
		10001-15000	28	28%
		>15000	10	10%
8	Religion	Hindu	58	58%
		Christian	9	9%
		Muslim	21	21%
		Any other	12	12%
9	Years spent in menopause	1-5 years	37	37%
		6-10 years	38	38%
		More than 10 years	25	25%

Table no. 4.1 shows the description of the study participants according to their demographic variables, the detailed description of the study participant according to each demographic characteristic is discussed further in the chapter. Fig 4.1 shows the description of study participant according to their age. Majority 40% of the study participants belonged to the category of 46-50 years and 13% of the study participants belonged to the category of 56-60 years of age. Fig 4.2 Pie diagram shows the description of study participant according to their marital status. Majority 91% of the study participants were married, whereas 9% of the study participants belonged to the category of Divorced/Widow. Fig 4.3 shows the description of study participant according to their education. Majority 41% of the study participants belonged to the category of illiterate whereas 2% of the study participants belonged to the Graduation/Post-graduate category of education. Fig 4.4 shows the description of study participant according to their working status. Majority 54% of the study participants were working, whereas 46% participants were not working. Fig 4.5 shows the description of study participant according to their occupational status. Majority 44% of the study participants were housewife by occupation whereas 2% of the study participants were government employee by occupation. Fig 4.6 shows the description of study participant according to their type of family. Majority 51% of the study participants were belonged to the nuclear family and 3% of the study participants belonged to the extended family.

Fig 4.9 shows the description of study participant according to the years spent in menopause. Majority 38% of the study participants were in the category of 6-10 years spent in menopause whereas 25% of the study participants were in the category of more than 10 years spent in menopause.

SECTION II : Description of menopausal symptoms of the study participants

This section deals with description of menopausal symptoms of the post-menopausal women residing in tribal area. The description of menopausal symptoms is described in three categories with frequency and percentage below.

Table 4.2. Description of menopausal symptoms of the study participants.

n=100

Menopausal Symptoms	F	%
Asymptomatic	33	33%
Mild to Moderate	55	55%
Severe to very Severe	12	12%

Table 4.2 shows the description of menopausal symptoms of the study participants, it reveals that majority 55% of the study participants experienced mild to moderate menopausal symptoms, followed by 33% of the study participants were in the asymptomatic category, whereas 12% of the study participants experienced severe to very severe symptoms.

Table 4.3. Description of menopausal symptoms of the study participants according to severity of the symptoms.

SR.NO.	Menopausal symptoms	Severity	F	%
1	Hot flushes	None	28	28%
		Mild	16	16%
		Moderate	20	20%
		Severe	21	21%
		Very severe	15	15%
2	Heart discomfort	None	37	37%
		Mild	18	18%
		Moderate	18	18%
		Severe	22	22%
		Very severe	5	5%

3	Sleep problems	None	25	25%
		Mild	17	17%
		Moderate	7	7%
		Severe	30	30%
		Very severe	21	21%
4	Depressive mood	None	33	33%
		Mild	9	9%
		Moderate	27	27%
		Severe	13	13%
		Very severe	18	18%
5	Irritability	None	21	21%
		Mild	14	14%
		Moderate	20	20%
		Severe	17	17%
		Very severe	28	28%
6	Anxiety	None	28	28%
		Mild	17	17%
		Moderate	17	17%
		Severe	9	9%
		Very severe	29	29%
7	Physical and mental exhaustion	None	19	19%
		Mild	16	16%
		Moderate	24	24%
		Severe	19	19%
		Very severe	22	22%
8	Sexual problems	None	28	28%
		Mild	21	21%
		Moderate	24	24%
		Severe	11	11%
		Very severe	16	16%
9	Bladder problems	None	37	37%
		Mild	14	14%
		Moderate	18	18%
		Severe	20	20%
		Very severe	9	9%
10	Dryness of vagina	None	26	26%
		Mild	24	24%
		Moderate	23	23%
		Severe	18	18%

		Very severe	9	9%
11	Joint and muscular discomfort	None	22	22%
		Mild	5	5%
		Moderate	29	29%
		Severe	13	13%
		Very severe	31	31%

Table no 4.3 shows description of the menopausal symptoms according to the severity of the symptoms. 72% of the study participants experienced hot flushes, Heart discomfort were experienced by the 63% of the study participants, 75% of the study participants experienced Sleep problems, 67% of the study participants experienced depressive mood, Irritability was experienced by 79% of the study participants, 72% of the study participants experienced Anxiety, 81% of the study participants experienced Physical and mental exhaustion, 72% of the study participants experienced sexual problems, Bladder problems were experienced by 63% of the study participants, 74% of the study participants experienced Dryness of vagina, Joint and muscular discomfort were experienced by 78% of the study participants.

SECTION III : Description of post-menopausal quality of life of the study participants

This section deals with description of post-menopausal quality of life of the post-menopausal women residing in tribal area. The description of post-menopausal quality of life is described in three categories with frequency and percentage below.

Table no 4.4. Description of post-menopausal quality of life of the study participants.

QOL	F	%
Poor	16	16%
Average	41	41%
Good	43	43%

Table no 4.4 shows the description of the post-menopausal quality of life of the study participants, it reveals that majority 43% of the participants had good quality of life, followed by 41% of the participants had average quality of life, and 16% of the participants had poor quality of life.

Section IV: Correlation between menopausal symptoms and post-menopausal quality of life of the study participants

This section deals with the correlation between menopausal symptoms and post-menopausal quality of life of the study participants. For determination of correlation between two variables Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient is used.

Table 4.5. Correlation between menopausal symptoms and post-menopausal quality of life.

n=100

Sr. No.	Variables	r' value	Interpretation
1.	Menopausal symptoms & Quality of life	-0.785	Strongly negative correlation

Table no 4.5 shows the correlation between menopausal symptoms and post-menopausal quality of life of the study participants residing at tribal area. The 'r' value -0.785 indicates strongly negative correlation between the menopausal symptoms and quality of life of the post-menopausal women residing at tribal areas of Bhandardara.

Discussion :

Findings related to demographic characteristics

In the present study, 100 post-menopausal women were included, majority of 40% of the study participants were belonged to the category of 46-50 years and 13% of the study participants belonged to the category of 56-60 years of age.

Marital status of the participants states that, majority 91% of the study participants were married, whereas 9% of the study participants belonged to the category of Divorced/Widow.

The data based on their education reveals that, majority 41% of the study participants were illiterate whereas 2% of the study participants belonged to the Graduation/Post-graduate category of education.

Working status of BLS/ACLS states that, majority 54% of the study participants were working, whereas 46% participants were not working.

Occupation of the study participants reveals that. Majority 44% of the study participants were housewife by occupation whereas 2% of the study participants were government employee by occupation.

The data based on the type of family states that, majority 51% of the study participants were belonged to the nuclear family and 3% of the study participants belonged to the extended family.

Monthly income of the family reveals that, 49% of the study participants were in the income category of 5001-10000 rupees, whereas 10% of the study participants were in the income category of more than 15000 rupees.

The data based on the religion of the study participants states that, majority 58% of the study participants were Hindu and 9% of the study participants were Christian.

The data based on the years spent in menopause by the study participants states that, majority 38% of the study participants were in the category of 6-10 years spent in menopause whereas 25% of the study participants were in the category of more than 10 years spent in menopause.

A similar study was conducted to assess the menopause-related symptoms and their impact on the women's life. The findings revealed that, among 150 postmenopausal women, 51 (34%) were in the age group of 55-59 years and more than half of the study population ($n = 116$, 77.3%) were married. The prevalence levels of the classical menopausal symptoms such as hot flushes, night sweats, and vaginal dryness in women aged 50-65 years were 75.3%, 58%, and 30.7%, respectively. The overall MENQOL mean total score was found as 112.47 ± 28.80 . The majority of them experienced the mean physical symptom, which was found to be 62.05 ± 17.82 . The associations between QOL scores with educational status and socioeconomic status were statistically highly significant with $P < 0.01$ and with marital status statistically significant with $P < 0.05$. The study concludes that, the post menopause related physical symptoms are frequently reported by the middle age group classifications.²⁷

Description of menopausal symptoms experienced by the study participants :

The present study assesses the menopausal symptoms of the post-menopausal women residing in tribal area. Findings regarding menopausal symptoms reveals that, majority 55% of the study participants experienced mild to moderate menopausal symptoms, followed by 33% of the study participants were in the asymptomatic category, whereas 12% of the study participants experienced severe to very severe symptoms.

Further findings regarding the severity of the menopausal symptoms reveals that, 72% of the study participants experienced hot flushes, Heart discomfort were experienced by the 63% of the study participants, 75% of the study participants experienced Sleep problems, 67% of the study participants experienced depressive mood, Irritability was experienced by 79% of the study participants, 72% of the study participants experienced Anxiety, 81% of the study participants experienced Physical and mental exhaustion, 72% of the study participants experienced sexual problems, Bladder problems were experienced by 63% of the study participants, 74% of the study participants experienced Dryness of vagina, Joint and muscular discomfort were experienced by 78% of the study participants.

A similar study was conducted to A community based cross-sectional study was conducted to assess prevalence of menopausal symptoms and its effect on quality of life among rural middle-aged women (40–60 years) of Haryana, India. Prevalence of menopausal symptoms was found to be 87.7%. Majority of the study subjects had anxiety (80%), followed by physical and mental exhaustion (71.5%), sleep problem (61.2%), irritability (60.7%), Joint and muscular discomfort (56%) and heart problems (54%). The most classical symptom of menopause i.e., hot flushes were reported in 36.7%. The mean age of menopause was 47.53 standard deviation 4.5 years. Statistically significant difference was seen for the mean score of few symptoms i.e., hot flushes, sweating ($P < 0.003$) and joint and muscular discomfort ($P < 0.014$) between post and peri-menopausal groups. The QOL was impaired in 70.2% of study subjects. The psychological symptoms attributed 70.8% to the poor QOL.²⁸

Description of post-menopausal QOL of the study participants

The present study assesses the post-menopausal QOL of the study participants, it reveals that, majority 43% of the participants had good quality of life, followed by 41% of the participants had average quality of life, and 16% of the participants had poor quality of life.

A similar study was conducted to assess the effects of menopausal symptoms on the QOL using Menopause-Specific QOL Questionnaire (MENQOL) among women in India. The study findings reveal that, the prevalence of symptoms in physical, vasomotor, psychological, and sexual domains was 74.56%, 60.7%, 44.68%, and 26.4%, respectively. An overall mean MENQOL score of physical ($27.1 + 0.72$), psychological ($2.01 + 0.27$), vasomotor ($4.08 + 0.79$), and sexual ($3.89 + 0.59$) health-related QOL among menopausal women showed poor QOL. Statistically significant differences were observed between the sociodemographic variables and the health-related QOL scores in all domains at $P < 0.05$. The study concludes that menopausal women-centred integrated model of care would empower women to lead improved health-related QOL in the next one-third of postmenopausal life span development.

Correlation between menopausal symptoms and post-menopausal quality of life of the study participants

The present study finding regarding the correlation between menopausal symptoms and post-menopausal quality of life of the study participants reveals that, the 'r' value -0.785 indicates strongly negative correlation between the menopausal symptoms and quality of life of the post-menopausal women residing at tribal areas of Bhandardara.

A similar study was conducted among 405 postmenopausal women to assess factors associated with quality of life of postmenopausal women living in Iran. The study findings reveal that, A negative correlation was found between the scores of QoL (total and all subscales) and the MRS total scores. The total scores of QoL were negatively correlated with duration of menopause ($r = -0.127$, $P = 0.010$), gravida ($r = -0.177$, $P < 0.001$), parity ($r = -0.165$, $P = 0.001$), frequency of stillbirth ($r = -0.104$, $P = 0.037$), vaginal delivery ($r = -0.161$, $P = 0.001$), and waist-to-hip ratio ($r = -0.195$, $P < 0.001$). The QoL total scores were positively correlated with the educational level of the participants ($r = 0.207$, $P < 0.001$) and that of their spouses ($r = 0.160$, $P = 0.001$) along with their level of monthly family income ($r = 0.218$, $P < 0.001$). Multiple-linear-regression analysis showed that the total score of QoL decreased with inadequate income, waist-to-hip ratio, and the total score of MRS.

Limitation :

This the study was the post-menopausal women residing at tribal area of Bhandardara selected by non-probability purposive sampling technique.

Conclusion

The study was performed to assess menopausal symptoms and post-menopausal quality of life of the women residing in tribal area. Majority of the participants found to be experiencing mild to moderate menopausal symptoms and good quality of life. The correlation between menopausal symptoms and post-menopausal quality of life shown strongly negative correlation.

Recommendations

- Replication of the study could be done with larger samples to validate and generalize the findings.
- A similar study can be done in another setting.
- The similar study can be done to evaluate effect of intervention reducing the severity of menopausal symptoms.

Acknowledgment :

The author of this study would like to acknowledge to all the participants.

Conflict of interest :- None to declare

Human Subjects : Consent was obtained by all participants in this study. Issues ethical approval from institutional ethics committee PIMS/SSEVPCON/R/IEC/PG/24/2023.

Author's contribution : All authors contributed in conceptualization of study, analysis and preparation of manuscript.

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